

INNOVATIVE IN TRAINING YOUNG VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS TO
TECHNICAL SKILLS APPROACH

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Annotation. This article provides information on how to improve the technical skills of young volleyball players on the basis of innovative approaches, the effective organization of the training process using the cluster method.

Key words: volleyball, young volleyball player, technique, skill, innovation, cluster, method, training.

It should be noted that the "Strategy of actions to implement the five priorities of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021", initiated by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of physical culture and sports, social and spiritual Five initiatives of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of physical culture and sports, Resolution No. PQ-3031 of June 3, 2017 "On measures for further development of physical culture and mass sports", March 5, 2018 PF-5368 "On measures to radically improve the system of public administration in the field of education" and other conceptual documents.

It is known that in sports, including volleyball, all technical and tactical actions are required to be performed in an emergency in a changing situation. Therefore, in the process of training in volleyball, training in technical and tactical movements, it is advisable to regularly develop the quality of agility with the help of sharply changing directional exercises. It depends on how the sports are organized and conducted to train and improve the skills of young athletes. In the organization of sports training, it is necessary to study the personal characteristics of athletes, to know their technical and tactical training. At the same time, in the example of young volleyball players, it is advisable to use innovative meaningful movement games and specialized pedagogical technologies to improve the quality of agility. In order to fully implement the above ideas, the coach needs the necessary knowledge and

skills. Conditions have been created for the young generation to regularly engage in physical culture and mass sports. Extensive work has been done to systematically organize the acquisition and targeted training.

The technology of effective training of volleyball players is effective in planning and managing the training process, assessing the level of physical and technical-tactical training, the formation of sports results, pre-competition training and control of competition activities.

However, these techniques have not yet been used in the training of volleyball players.

At present, the most effective methods of preparing one-sided loads in the training sessions of secondary school students are the priority ones. It is important and relevant to introduce these methods in the training of athletes in volleyball and to conduct special research.

Volleyball differs from other sports in its essence, content and features. The volleyball game is played on a relatively small 18x9-meter rectangular court divided into two equal parts in the middle. (Figure 1)

Modern volleyball is extremely rich in various game skills and tactical combinations, and passes with great intensity and speed. Consequently, the above-mentioned characteristics of the sport of volleyball require perfect technical skills from the players. The more extensive the technical skills in the competition and the more perfectly formed they are against external influences, the better the chances of winning.

Game technique is a specialized action or set of actions performed simultaneously and in a specific order. Game technique - should be designed to be precise, fast, light, situational, low-energy and high-performance. Volleyball technique is divided into two

main parts: offensive and defensive technique. In turn, the above sections are divided into several groups according to the form and content of technical methods. Each group will have its own way of performing technical actions (Template 3).

Attack technique

Cases. In a volleyball game, players must move the ball as quickly as possible. Therefore, in this or that game, the player needs to be well prepared to play with the ball. To this end, it is necessary to assume different situations in order to perform different modes of action.

When attacking and blocking - high, when receiving the ball into the game - medium, when receiving an attacking shot or a ball returning from the obstacle - low (Figure 2). In this case, the position of the TCOG (total center of gravity) depends on the nature of the next movement. It should also be noted that the height of the player and his coordination ability have a significant impact on the TCOG. Therefore, the effective standing position should be such that the TCOG can be quickly removed from the base and allowed to move and operate as needed.

Stand-ups can be static (motionless) or dynamic (receiving the ball by moving the main base from one foot to the other, waiting for an attack or blocking), depending on the nature of the application of the next movement. . In this position, the arms are at the waist, the fingers are facing the palms, and the body is slightly bent forward. The body should be free.

Movement. The player moves across the field to perform a certain technique. Depending on the method and the situation in the game, you can take steps (forward, backward, sideways), jump, jump, run, fall and perform various actions. The movements of stepping and running are much softer (due to the slower vibration of the

UOM). Stepping to the side is often used when blocking a small distance, receiving an attacking shot, or receiving a ball that has returned from an obstacle by changing its direction. The movement always starts with the foot closest to the desired direction of movement. It is used to perform quick response actions from jumping, jumping and running. The actions considered are often used in conjunction. Preliminary cases. The initial circumstances determine the phase of preparation for the implementation of this or that technique. The acquisition of preconditions must provide a favorable environment and mobility for the expected action. Regardless of the execution of the technical method, the initial cases are somewhat static: before passing the ball (Fig. 3 a), when receiving the ball from below (Fig. 3 b), when blocking (3 v- picture) and when delivering an attack kick (Fig. 3 g-2.picture).

Conclusion. Today, in the context of Uzbekistan, the creation of a new mechanism in the higher education system has become a vital necessity, which must ensure mutual control, competition and mutual benefit between the types of education. Given the high social significance of higher education for the sustainable development

of society, modern requirements, problems in the system and the gap between education, science and industry in solving them today necessitate the transition of continuous pedagogical education to a cluster development model.

In the process of training in volleyball, technical and tactical movements, it is advisable to regularly develop the quality of agility with the help of sharply changing directional exercises. It depends on how the sports are organized and conducted to train and improve the skills of young athletes.

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